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Title: Gas-particle distributions, sources and health effects of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs), Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) and Polychlorinated Naphthalenes (PCNs) in Venice aerosols

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Abstract: Air samples were collected in Venice during summer 2009 and 2012 to measure gas and particulate concentrations of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polychlorinated naphthalenes (PCNs). PCB-11, considered a marker for non-Aroclor contamination of the environment, was found for the first time in the Venetian lagoon and in Europe. An investigation on sources has been conducted, evidencing traffic as major source of PAHs, whereas PCBs have a similar composition to Aroclor 1248 and 1254; in 2009 a release of PCN-42 has been hypothesized. Toxicological evaluation by TCA and TEQ method, conducted for the first time in Venice air samples, identified BaP, PCB-126 and PCB-169 as the most important contributors to the total carcinogenic activity of PAHs and the total dioxin-like activity of PCBs and PCNs.

- Gas-particle distribution of POPs in Venice is discussed
- PCB-11 was found for the first time in aerosols in Venice and Europe
- A high concentration of PCN-42 in 2009 samples was measured
- Traffic was the major source of PAHs
- A toxicological evaluation by TCA and TEQ method was conducted

TITLE

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2 Gas-particle distributions, sources and health effects of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs),
3 Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) and Polychlorinated Naphthalenes (PCNs) in Venice aerosols
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1. Introduction

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3 Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and polychlorinated
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5 naphthalenes (PCNs) are semi-volatile organic compounds that are persistent and ubiquitous in the
6
7 environment. PAHs can be produced by incomplete combustion from natural origins (e. g.
8
9 volcanism, natural fires) or from anthropogenic origins (e. g. combustion of timber, waste, fossil
10
11 fuels). PCBs were first synthesized in 1929 and were widely used as dielectric fluids, hydraulic
12
13 fluids and in many other applications until they were banned in the late 1970s (Desaules et al.,
14
15 2008). PCNs were used in the electrical industry owing to their water-repellent, flame-retardant,
16
17 dielectric and fungus-resistant properties. In addition, PCNs can be unintentionally generated by
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19 several industrial processes and by incomplete combustion from waste incinerators (Manodori et al.,
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21 2006a). Because of their toxicity and low reactivity PAHs, PCBs and PCNs are classified as POPs
22
23 (Persistent Organic Pollutants) (Helm and Bidleman, 2003; UNECE, 1998).

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31 POPs are affected by long-range atmospheric transport (LRAT) and their presence has been
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33 discovered in remote environments such as the Arctic (Hung et al., 2005; Polkowska et al., 2011)
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35 and Antarctica (Dickhut et al., 2012; Klanova et al., 2008; Negri et al., 2006). Bioaccumulation of
36
37 these substances can cause adverse effects on human health including reproductive and immune
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39 effects, developmental anomalies and cancer (Desaules et al., 2008; Gambaro et al., 2004).

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43 Generally the atmospheric burden of POPs is relatively small compared to other environmental
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45 constituents but air is considered the most important pathway for their global redistribution (Piazza
46
47 et al., 2013).

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51 PAHs, PCBs and PCNs exist in the atmosphere as vapor phase chemicals and in a condensed form
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53 where they are adsorbed on atmospheric particles. Gas to particle partition of pollutants depends on
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55 molecular weight, atmospheric conditions (temperature, humidity, precipitation), the nature (origin
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57 and properties) of the aerosol, interactions between the compounds and the aerosol and the overall
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59 behavior of compounds in the atmosphere (Hassan and Khoder, 2012). The distribution between the
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1 gaseous and particle-bound phases is the most important factor determining removal mechanisms
2 and residence time in the atmosphere (Gambaro et al., 2004). This distribution strongly influences
3
4 POPs transport and how pollutants enter the human body. Therefore, the evaluation of gas-particle
5
6 distribution of pollutants in atmosphere has received worldwide attention. Studies of POPs in the
7
8 Venice lagoon have principally focused on sediments (Frignani et al., 2004, 2001; Moret et al.,
9
10 2001) and surface waters (Manodori et al., 2006b; Moret et al., 2005) but very little is known about
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12 the role of aerosols in the transport of pollutants into the lagoon system and the gas-particle
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14 partition of POPs in this area.
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20 The first objective of this work is to characterize the gas-particle distribution profile of atmospheric
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22 PAHs, PCBs and PCNs. Due to the importance of estimating the possible origin of pollutants in
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24 this area, we examined the sources of PAHs, using the diagnostic ratios method. This study presents
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26 the first Venetian lagoon samples that evaluate the toxicological activities of PAHs and the dioxin-
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28 like activity of PCBs while focusing on the differences between gas and particulate toxicological
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30 characteristics.
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36 **2. Material and methods**

37 ***2.1. Reagents and materials***

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39 Pesticide-grade dichloromethane, n-hexane and toluene (Romil Ltd., Cambridge, UK) were used.
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41 All isotope-labelled standard solutions (EC-1434, EC-1426, EC-4187, EC-4188, EC-4189, CLM-
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43 2477, CLM-2722, CLM-3757, CLM-2451) were acquired from CIL (Cambridge Isotope
44
45 Laboratories Inc., USA); PAHs native standard solutions (PAH Mix 9) were purchased from Dr.
46
47 Ehrenstorfer GmbH (Germany); PCBs native solutions (C-CS-01, -02, -03 and -05) were obtained
48
49 from AccuStandard Inc. (USA); PCNs native standard solution (ECN-5178) was acquired from
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51 CIL. All the tools and glassware were washed with an aqueous 5% (v/v) Contrad® solution (Decon
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53 Laboratories Limited, UK), dried and rinsed with dichloromethane and n-hexane.
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2.2. Sample collection

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3 Sixteen samples were collected on the Sacca San Biagio island (Lat. 45°25'40.14'' N; Long.
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5 12°18'36.73'' E), which is located along the Giudecca Canal, southeast of the historical center. The
6
7 island is not inhabited, permitting an evaluation of the sources of pollutants in Venice without the
8
9 influence of an extremely local source. Venice and surrounding areas are heavily affected by
10
11 anthropogenic activities such as industrial emissions from the Porto Marghera industrial area and
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13 traffic pollution from the nearby Mestre motorway. The Sacca San Biagio island site is influenced
14
15 by ship traffic (public transport, touristic and merchant shipping), aircraft flying to the Venice
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17 Airport and domestic heating (Stortini et al., 2009). Five samples were collected from August to
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19 September 2009 and eleven samples from July to October 2012. More details about the sampling
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21 dates and meteorological conditions during the sampling period are given in Table A.1.
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28 Samples were collected using a high volume air sampler (AirFlowPUF, Analitica Strumenti, Italy;
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30 flow rate: 0.3 m³ min⁻¹), useful to keep gaseous and particulate phases separated. Air is first drawn
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32 through a quartz fiber filter (QFF, porosity 1 µm, size 102 mm, SKC Inc., USA) where particulate
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34 matter is entrapped and then through a polyurethane foam plug (PUF, height 75 mm, diameter 65
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36 mm, SKC Inc., USA) to collect vapor-phase compounds. PUFs and QFFs were replaced every 2-3
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38 days. Before sampling, QFFs were furnace-treated at 400°C for 4 h and PUFs were pre-cleaned by
39
40 extracting with toluene using the Pressurized Liquid Extractor (PLE, Fluid Management Systems
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42 Inc., USA) under the following working conditions: 100°C temperature, 1000 psi pressure, 7 min
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44 static duration, 2 cycles. The QFFs were then individually wrapped in a double aluminum foil.
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48 QFFs and PUFs were stored at -20°C after sampling until extraction. Overall 8 field blanks were
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53 collected in order to determine any contamination during sample handling and preparation.
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2.3. Analysis

1 A unique analytical method was used for PCBs, PCNs and PAHs (Piazza et al., 2013). Blanks and
2 samples were spiked with a known amount of an isotopically labelled compounds mixture
3
4 containing 21 ¹³C-labelled PCBs 40 pg μL⁻¹ and 3 ¹³C-labelled PAHs 1 ng μL⁻¹ prior to extraction,
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6 PUFs and QFFs were extracted separately with a n-hexane/dichloromethane mixture (1:1, v/v) for
7
8 three times using a Pressurized Liquid Extractor and the previously described conditions. Cleaning
9
10 was performed by injecting the extracts onto a disposable neutral silica column using the automated
11
12 PowerPrep system (Fluid Management Systems Inc.). Before the instrumental analysis each blank
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14 and sample was spiked with a known amount of the recovery standard solution containing ¹³C-
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16 chrysene at 1 ng μL⁻¹, ¹³C PCB- 47 and ¹³C PCB- 141 at 40 pg μL⁻¹.
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22 We determined fifteen of the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, 1981) priority PAHs:
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24 acenaphthylene (ACY), acenaphthene (ACE), fluorene (FL), phenanthrene (PHE), anthracene
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26 (ANT), fluoranthene (FLT), pyrene (PYR), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA), chrysene (CHR),
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28 benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF), benzo[k]fluoranthene (BkF), benzo[a]pyrene (BaP),
29
30 benzo[ghi]perylene (BghiP), indeno[1,2,3-c,d]pyrene (IcdP) and dibenzo[a,h]anthracene (DahA).
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32
33 The determination of PAHs was conducted with a quadrupole mass-spectrometer (Agilent 5975C,
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35 Agilent Technologies, USA), operating in electron impact mode (EI 70 eV), coupled with an
36
37 Agilent 7890A (Agilent Technologies) gas chromatograph, equipped with a 60-m fused silica
38
39 capillary column (0.25 mm I. D.; 0.25 μm; Agilent Technologies). Gas-chromatograph operating
40
41 conditions are the following: injector temperature 290 °C; transfer line temperature 290 °C; oven
42
43 temperature program 70 °C (1.5 min), 10 °C min⁻¹ to 150 °C (10 min), 3 °C min⁻¹ to 280 °C (28
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45 min), 20 °C min⁻¹ to 300°C (0 min), 305° for 30 min (post-run); carrier gas (helium) 1 mL min⁻¹;
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47 splitless inject mode (split valve open after 1.5 min) with purge flow 50 mL min⁻¹.
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55 Samples were analyzed for 127 of the 209 congeners of PCB. The selected PCBs reflect the
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57 composition of Aroclor technical mixtures. Dioxin-like priority congeners as defined by the 2005
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59 World Health Organization Toxic Equivalency Factors (WHO-TEF) (Van den Berg et al., 2006)
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1 were also included. 106 chromatographic peaks representing 126 PCB congeners (15 as double and
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4 DiCBs, 17 TriCBs, 22 TeCBs, 24 PeCBs, 22 HxCBs, 17 HpCBs, 7 OcCBs, 3 NoCB and the sole
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6 DeCB. 6 PCNs were determined: PCN-27, PCN-42, PCN-52, PCN-67, PCN-73 and PCN-75. A
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8 MAT 95XP (Thermo Finnigan) high-resolution mass spectrometer (10000) equipped with a
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10 Hewlett–Packard Model 6890 gas chromatograph was used to analyze PCBs and PCNs. The gas
11
12 chromatographic separation was executed on a 60-m HP-5MS column (0.25 mm I.D., 0.25 μm ;
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14 Agilent Technologies) operating with the following conditions: injector temperature 300 °C;
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16 transfer line temperature 300 °C; oven temperature program 90 °C (1 min), 20 °C min^{-1} to 150 °C
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18 (8 min), 4 °C min^{-1} to 235 °C (10 min), 12 °C min^{-1} to 290°C, 290°C for 34 min (postrun); carrier
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20 gas (helium), 1.2 mL min^{-1} ; inject mode, splitless (split valve open after 1 min) with purge flow 50
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22 mL min^{-1} . Quantification was performed using internal standards and the isotopic dilution
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24 technique. PCNs were quantified using selected ^{13}C -PCBs peaks for each class of homologues.
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26 Results were corrected for the instrumental response factor.
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The limit of detection (LOD, Table A.3) was calculated from the mean blank value plus three standard deviation. PUFs and QFFs samples concentrations, that were above the limit of detection, were corrected for the corresponding average field blank (FB, Table A.2). The accuracy of the analytical method was tested on Standard Reference Material (NIST) 1649b (Urban Dust) and 2585 (Organic Contaminants in House Dust), during the set up of the method: recoveries, laboratory and procedural blanks have been reported by Piazza et al. (2013).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Gaseous and particulate PAHs concentration

The total concentration of PAHs (gas + particulate) ranged from 3.0 to 7.9 ng m^{-3} in 2009 and from 1.5 to 5.2 ng m^{-3} in 2012. They are similar to that reported in previous studies in the Venice Lagoon

1 (Contini et al., 2011; Gambaro et al., 2004). Comparison with relevant data from other urban sites
2 shows that the total PAHs concentration observed in this study is lower than that measured in urban
3 areas in Tuscany (0.92-13 ng m⁻³ in PM_{2.5}) (Martellini et al., 2012) and in Portugal (average of 70
4 ng m⁻³) (Slezakova et al., 2013) and much lower than levels of Kolaeli, an industrial city of Turkey
5 (108 ng m⁻³) (Gaga et al., 2012) and Alessandria (summer season: 330-1770 ng m⁻³) (Khairy and
6 Lohmann, 2013).
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10 Concentration of single congeners ranged from a few pg m⁻³ to a few ng m⁻³ for phenantrene (Table
11 1). Atmospheric PAHs in the Venice Lagoon are predominant in gaseous form, both in 2009 and in
12 2012. In 2009, the median gaseous PAHs concentration was 3.9 ng m⁻³, while the median
13 concentration of PAHs associated with particles was 0.82 ng m⁻³. In 2012 the median total
14 concentration of PAHs was 2.1 ng m⁻³ and 0.34 ng m⁻³ in the gaseous and particulate form,
15 respectively, with a median G/P (gas/particulate) ratio of 3.2 in 2009 and 7.6 in 2012. G/P
16 calculated for 2009 samples is similar to those reported in a previous study in the Venice Lagoon,
17 referred to summer 2002 (Gambaro et al., 2004) and in other studies (Cincinelli et al., 2007; Hassan
18 and Khoder, 2012), while G/P for 2012 samples is much closer to the ratio found in Birmingham,
19 UK (Harrison et al., 1996). The distribution of compounds between gaseous and particulate phases
20 is dependent upon temperature, air humidity, property of adsorption surface, available adsorption
21 surface, molecular weight and vapor pressure. In particular, high ambient temperatures could
22 change the distribution of chemicals between the two phases by increasing the vapor pressure of
23 compounds and favoring their volatilization from the particulate to the gaseous phase (Hassan and
24 Khoder, 2012).
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51 Despite differences in the gas-particle partition between 2009 and 2012, the congener profile was
52 similar (Figure 1). PHE, FLA and PYR were the most abundant PAHs, representing about 80% of
53 total PAHs; other congeners were always under 6% of Σ PAHs. Also gaseous congeners profile was
54 similar in the two sets of samples: gaseous phase was dominated by low molecular weight PAHs:
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1 taken together PHE, FLA and PYR represented almost the 90% of total PAHs in gaseous form.
2 Particulate was characterized by a more complex distribution of congeners and showed a little
3 difference between the two sets of samples. Particulate from 2009 campaign was dominated by IcdP
4 (20% of Σ PAH) and BghiP (19% of Σ PAH), while in 2012 samples PYR (21% of Σ PAH) and FLA
5 (18% of Σ PAH) were the most abundant compounds. As shown in Figure 2, in both cases, PAHs
6 with 5 or 6 aromatic rings were predominant in particulate matter (PM). These profiles are
7 comparable to those reported in a previous study regarding PAHs in the Venice Lagoon (Gambaro
8 et al., 2004), similar to PAHs profile investigated in UK (Mandalakis et al., 2002), but different
9 from that reported in other studies (e.g. in Egypt (Hassan and Khoder, 2012) and in Taiwan (Fang et
10 al., 2004)). The strong correlation between PAHs distribution and molecular weight is in good
11 agreement with other studies (Cincinelli et al., 2007; Hassan and Khoder, 2012): low molecular
12 weight PAHs are generally more volatile than high molecular weight PAHs, thus it is more probable
13 to find them in the gaseous form while the opposite situation occurs for the heaviest PAHs.
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31 ***3.2. Gaseous and particulate PCBs concentration***

32 Table 2 summarizes homologue groups, for indicator PCBs (PCB-28, 52, 101, 118, 138, 153, 180)
33 and dioxin-like congeners (PCB-77, 81, 105, 114, 118, 123, 126, 156, 157, 167, 169, 189). We
34 report the congener PCB-11 (3,3'-dichlorobiphenyl), an original non-Aroclor compound largely
35 deriving from consumer goods containing azo- and phthalocyanine pigments. Recently PCB-11 has
36 been found as a contaminant in various environments worldwide and even in polar aerosols (Piazza
37 et al., 2013; Rodenburg et al., 2010; Rodenburg and Meng, 2013).
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51 The total median concentration of PCBs (gas + particulate) was 0.99 ng m^{-3} in 2009 samples and
52 0.35 ng m^{-3} in 2012 samples; they are higher than that reported in a few previous studies in the
53 Venice Lagoon (Manodori et al., 2007, 2006c), and closer to that reported by Gambaro et al. (2004).
54 Comparison with relevant data from urban sites shows that the total PCBs concentration observed
55 in this study are similar to those measured in a highly industrialized city of northern Italy (Colombo
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1 et al., 2013), lower than in Chicago air (Rodenburg and Meng, 2013) and in Turkey (Yenisoy-
2 Karakaş et al., 2012) and higher than those reported for the urban air of Dalian (China) (Xu et al.,
3 2013). The most present congeners (> 5%) were PCB-84+101+90 in 2009 samples, PCB-47+48 and
4 PCB-71+41+64 in 2012 samples. PCBs were predominant in the gaseous form. In 2009 the Σ PCBs
5 concentration ranged from 470 pg m^{-3} to 1300 pg m^{-3} in gaseous phase and from 7.9 pg m^{-3} to 330
6 pg m^{-3} in particulate phase. In 2012 the median total concentrations of PCBs was 350 pg m^{-3} and
7 0.95 pg m^{-3} in the gaseous and particulate form respectively, with a G/P ratio of 8.9 in 2009 and 190
8 in 2012. G/P ratio for 2009 was higher than that reported by Yenisoy-Karakaş et al. (2012) and
9 lower than that calculated in other studies conducted in the Venice Lagoon (Gambaro et al., 2004)
10 and in northern Italy (Castro-Jimenez et al., 2009), while our 2012 G/P ratio was higher than those
11 reported by all that studies.
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27 Figure 3 shows the distribution of PCBs, classified on chlorine number. In 2009 samples the order
28 of the homologues was the following: PeCBs (28% of Σ PCBs) > TeCBs (26% of Σ PCBs) > TriCBs
29 (13% of Σ PCBs). In 2012 the distribution was dominated by the TeCBs (60% of Σ PCBs), followed
30 by PeCBs (15% of Σ PCBs) and TriCBs (10% of Σ PCBs). As reported in Figure 4, in both cases,
31 the gaseous form was dominated by the TeCBs. The primary homologues in the particulate phase
32 were PeCBs in 2009, constituting 40% of total PCBs, while in 2012 PeCBs, TeCBs, TriCBs and
33 HpCBs contribute with similar values to Σ PCBs. As expected, the lighter congeners were
34 concentrated in the gaseous phase (MoCBs to PeCBs account for 86-89% of Σ PCB) while in
35 particulate matter about 78-95% of total PCBs concentration was represented by intermediate
36 molecular weight PCBs (TriCBs to HpCBs). The pattern of PCBs found in Venice, with TeCBs and
37 PeCBs as primary homologues, is similar to the composition of the commercial mixtures Aroclor
38 1248, that is characterized by 49% of TeCBs and Aroclor 1254, in which 53% of PCBs is
39 represented by PeCBs (Erickson, 2001).
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1 Total PCB-11 median concentration was 14 pg m^{-3} in 2009 and 4.9 pg m^{-3} in 2012. To the best of
2 our knowledge this is the first detection of PCB-11 in the Venetian Lagoon and in aerosol samples
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4 from Europe. Detected concentrations are significantly similar to that reported by Du et al. (2009)
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6 and lower than those found in other urban areas such as Chicago (24 pg m^{-3}) (Hu et al., 2008) and
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8 also remote Arctic (95 pg m^{-3}) and Antarctic (19 pg m^{-3}) sites (Choi et al., 2008). Other authors
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10 found comparable levels of PCB-11 in Antarctic air (Li et al., 2012; Piazza et al., 2013).
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14 The identification of PCB-11 in the Venice lagoon is significant because it is a congener that has to
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16 be associated with specific sources other than the release from commercial mixtures. Effectively,
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18 although commercial PCB production was banned in 1979 by EPA (EPA, 1979), a concentration of
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20 up to 50 ppm of certain manufacturing by-product PCBs was allowed. Recently congeners related
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22 to this origin have been identified in water (Rodenburg et al., 2010), sediments (Hu et al., 2011) and
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24 air (Hu et al., 2008), creating great concern. PCB-11 seems to be a marker of non-Aroclor PCB
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26 contamination; its presence in the environment cannot be associated to breakdown or dechlorination
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28 of heavier congeners from commercial mixtures (Grossman, 2013). Rodenburg et al. (2010)
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30 identified PCB-11 in several consumer goods such as paper from color magazines and newspapers,
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32 cardboard from food packaging and plastic grocery bags in New York. They demonstrated that the
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34 use of diarylide yellow pigments in consumer goods results in the dispersion of PCB-11 throughout
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36 the environment. Relatively little is known about the toxicity of PCB-11 although it produces
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38 neurochemical effects in rat cerebral cells and may exhibit dioxin-like toxicity (Rodenburg et al.,
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3.3. Gaseous and particulate PCNs concentration

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67 The median concentration of PCNs in Venice air was 89 pg m^{-3} in 2009 and 0.29 pg m^{-3} in 2012. In
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69 general samples were dominated by low molecular weight PCNs. In 2012 samples TeCNs and
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71 PeCNs account together for 81% of Σ PCN; the most abundant congener was PCN-52 even if
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73 relevant abundances have been also detected for PCN-42 and PCN-27; the gas-particle distribution

1 was shifted toward the gas phase and most PCNs values in QFFs samples were below LOD. 2009
2 samples were dominated by PCN-42, representing 99% of Σ PCNs. PCNs concentration in gas and
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4 particulate phase and the corresponding G/P, calculated for values above LOD, are reported in
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7 Table 3.
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10 The scarcity of information regarding PCNs in the Venice lagoon makes a comparison quite hard.
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12 The only data available on PCNs in this area was given by Manodori et al. (2006a). They reported a
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14 Σ PCNs concentration ranging from 0.19 pg m^{-3} to 0.80 pg m^{-3} in the marine sampling site. Median
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16 concentration measured in the Venice lagoon in 2009 was similar to those reported for England
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18 (Lee et al., 2005) and higher than those measured in China (Lin et al., 2013) and Canada (Helm and
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20 Bidleman, 2003); in 2012 concentration of PCNs was lower than that showed by all these studies.
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22 Σ PCNs/ Σ PCBs ratio was very different from other regions worldwide: in 2009 PCBs concentration
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24 was about 1200 times higher than PCNs levels; in 2009 Σ PCNs/ Σ PCBs ratio was 0.09, while in
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26 England Σ PCNs/ Σ PCBs ratios were close to or even greater than 1 in various sites (Lee et al.,
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3.4. Sources estimation

66 Generally, each PAH source provides an individual profile fingerprint or signature, although
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68 sometimes there is much similarity and overlap between profiles from different source categories
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70 (Harrison et al., 1996). In this study we measured high concentrations of PHE, FLA and PYR,
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72 which Ravindra et al. (2008) correlated both to emissions from motor vehicles and from
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74 incineration. Moreover, oil combustion was reported to be associated with high concentrations of
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76 FL, FLA and PYR (Ravindra et al., 2008). Diagnostic ratios (DR) can help evaluate the possible
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78 PAHs sources. Congeners of molecular masses 178 and 202 are commonly used to distinguish
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80 between combustion and petroleum sources. For mass 178 the ANT/(ANT+PHE) ratio <0.10 is
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82 usually taken as an indicator of petroleum, while a ratio >0.10 indicates a dominance of combustion
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84 sources. For mass 202 Yunker et al (2002) identify the ratio FLA/(FLA+PYR) of 0.50 as the
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1 petroleum/combustion transition point, although it is less definitive than $ANT/(ANT+PHE)$ while
2 Ravindra et al. (2008) use the same ratio to distinguish between gasoline (<0.50) and diesel (>0.50)
3 emission. PAHs of molecular mass 228 can also be used as indicators. A $BaA/(BaA+CHR)$ ratio
4 <0.20 implies petroleum, while ratios from 0.20 to 0.35 indicate either petroleum or combustion
5 and $BaA/(BaA+CHR) >0.35$ implies combustion sources (Yunker et al., 2002). The ratio of the sum
6 of FL, PYR, BaA, CHR, BbF, BkF, BaP, BghiP and IcdP (CPAH) on the total concentration of
7 PAHs (ΣPAH) is much closer to 1 as the combustion is an important source of PAHs. A BbF/BkF
8 ratio higher than 0.5 or an $IcdP/(IcdP+BghiP)$ ratio between 0.35 and 0.70 indicate diesel emission
9 (Ravindra et al., 2008).
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22 Interpretation of DR greatly depends on the ratio considered and on the source profile chosen. Since
23 it would be difficult to differentiate sources based on only one of the proposed methods in this work
24 we calculated the following DRs based on total PAHs concentration (sum of g-PAH and p-PAH): a)
25 $ANT/(ANT+PHE)$; b) $BaA/(BaA+CHR)$; c) $CPAH/\Sigma PAH$; d) $FLA/(FLA+PYR)$; e) BbF/BkF ; f)
26 $IcdP/(IcdP+BghiP)$. As shown in Figure 5 all samples have an $ANT/(ANT+PHE)$ ratio much lower
27 than 0.10 (0.004-0.053) indicating petrogenic sources as a probable PAH source. The $CPAH/\Sigma PAH$
28 ratio was far from 1 for all samples (0.26-0.52), while $BaA/(BaA+CHR)$ values (0.13-0.25) are
29 located between the petrogenic and mixed sources zone in the graphic. $FLA/(FLA+PYR)$ ranges
30 from 0.44 to 0.71, indicating the presence of both diesel and gasoline contributions. The BbF/BkF
31 ratio (1.1-5.3) is significantly higher than 0.5 for all samples, suggesting an important diesel
32 emission, while all calculated $IcdP/(IcdP+BghiP)$ ratios (0.78-1.00) are out of the typical range of
33 diesel emission of 0.35-0.70. Results suggest a probable petrogenic origin for PAHs in the Venice
34 lagoon yet a distinction between diesel and gasoline emissions is not possible. 2009 and 2012
35 samples showed similar diagnostic ratios, suggesting that the sampling site has been affected by the
36 same sources over the years.
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Several authors reported that the pattern of PCBs is related to the transport of the compounds in the atmosphere (Manodori et al., 2006c; Piazza et al., 2013; Yeo et al., 2003). These studies found a high concentration of PeCBs in urban areas and a greater concentration of low molecular weight compounds (e. g. TriCBs) than other homologues in rural areas. Wania and Mackay (1996) supposed that the heaviest homologues could easily deposit on plants, soils and layers of water and are less likely to evaporate into the atmosphere due to their lower vapor pressure. More volatile species mostly exist as gases in the atmosphere and are affected by LRAT. The distribution of PCBs in the Venice lagoon (Figure 3), with TeCBs and PeCBs as most present homologues, could be interpreted as a result of both short- and long-range atmospheric transport. No other consideration can be made on the sources of PCBs, because of the small number of samples.

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Although PCNs have been banned since 1977, they can be emitted from PCN products or from evaporation from contaminated soil. Combustion activities such as coal, wood, waste or biomass open burning can also release PCNs. Research has suggested that the contribution of combustion sources to the PCN burden in environmental media has been increasing over the past decades. Many studies have identified certain PCN congeners that are absent or occur at low levels in commercial PCNs and PCBs mixtures but are enriched in combustion results (Bidleman et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2012). Samples analyzed in this study showed a high variability in composition. PCN content in 2009 samples was constituted almost completely by PCN-42: it is not considered a combustion marker and is present in low concentrations in Aroclor/Halowax mixtures. On the other hand, in 2012, the most present congener was PCN-52 in the gaseous phase (33% of gaseous \sum PCNs), that has been related to combustion (Bidleman et al., 2010); PCN-42 was present, accounting for 22% of total PCNs concentration. The different composition observed between the two campaigns leads to the hypothesis of a different source of PCNs over the years and suggests a significant release of PCN-42 in 2009: excluding PCN-42 the \sum sPCNs concentration in 2009 was 0.83 (0.59-1.1) pg m^{-3}

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in PUFs and n. d. (n. d.-0.75 pg m⁻³) in QFFs, reaching values close to that measured in 2012 (Table 3) and in previous campaigns (Manodori et al., 2006a).

3.5. Health risk assessment

Benzo[a]pyrene has been regarded by the World Health Organization as the most appropriate indicator in order to evaluate the carcinogenicity of PAHs in air. Many countries use BaP concentrations to estimate the overall carcinogenicity of a mixture of PAHs. In Italy the fixed limit value for BaP in PM₁₀ is 1 ng m⁻³ (Legislative Decree, 2010). Although BaP appears to be the best indicator, the use of BaP concentration alone will probably underestimate the carcinogenic potential of airborne PAHs mixtures as co-occurring substances are also carcinogenic (WHO, 2003). The health risk associated with the inhalation of carcinogenic PAHs in the study area was estimated by using toxic equivalency factors (TEFs): BaP equivalent concentrations for each congener were calculated by multiplying the individual PAH concentration by its corresponding TEF_{BaP} value, that ranges from 0.001 to 1 for BaP and DahA (Cincinelli et al., 2007; Hassan and Khoder, 2012; Nisbet and Lagoy, 1992). In Table 4 the average BaP equivalent concentrations (BaP_{eq}) and the contribution to the total carcinogenic activity (TCA) of each individual compound are summarized.

Using the TEF approach, BaP was identified as the compound that most contributes to the total carcinogenic activity of PAHs in Venice air, both in 2009 and 2012 (53% and 69%, in 2009 and 2012, respectively). This result confirms the importance of the choice of BaP as a marker of overall carcinogenicity, but underlines that also other congeners can play a role in the total carcinogenicity of the mixture, contributing up to 17% to TCA (Table 4). In all samples, TCA detected values were significantly below the Italian limit of 1 ng m⁻³ for BaP.

In the particulate phase BaP exhibited the highest contribution to TCA (48% in 2009 and 72% in 2012). In the gaseous phase the most dominant compounds were PHE (24%) and BaA (24%) in 2009 and BaP (44%) in 2012. Although total g-PAHs concentration was much higher than p-PAHs

1 concentrations, the particulate matter in Venice air was more carcinogenic than gas, contributing for
2 95% in 2009 and 78% in 2012 to the total carcinogenic activity of both phases. This result is due to
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4 the gas-particle distribution of PAHs where the particulate phase was dominated by high molecular
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6 weight PAHs that are considered more carcinogenic than low molecular weight PAHs. Thus even
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8 small quantities of such compounds can make the particulate very dangerous for human health.
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10 Lighter PAHs have higher concentrations in the gaseous phase than in particulate matter thus,
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12 despite their weak carcinogenicity, they can also significantly contribute to TCA. Over the years a
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14 decreasing of the global TCA has been observed, due to the lower content of carcinogenic
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16 compounds, such as BaP and DahA (TEF_{BaP}: 1) in QFFs samples in 2012, respect to 2009.
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22 In addition to PAHs, PCBs and PCNs with a similar structure to 2,3,7,8-tetrachloro-p-dioxin
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24 (TCDD) also exert dioxin-like biological and toxic effects. The World Health Organization
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26 developed a suit of TEFs for dioxin-like PCBs (non-ortho and mono-ortho PCBs) and PCNs with
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28 planar structure and four lateral chlorines at the 2,3,6,7 positions. The value 1 is assigned to 2,3,7,8-
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30 tetrachloro-p-dioxin. The average TCDD equivalent concentrations (TCDD_{eq}) and the contribution
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32 to the toxic equivalency (TEQ) of each individual PCB and PCN are reported in Table 5.
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38 The total dioxin-like toxicity, expressed as TEQ, was 26 fg m⁻³ in 2009 and 5.8 fg m⁻³ in 2012. They
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40 are higher than that measured in the Arctic Ocean, but similar to that reported for Chicago
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42 (Bidleman et al., 2010). Considering that an adult of 60 kg daily inhales a volume of 15 m³ of air
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44 (Lin et al., 2013), the average daily intake of dioxin-like compounds was 6.5 fg kg⁻¹ day⁻¹ in 2009
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46 and 1.5 fg kg⁻¹ day⁻¹ in 2012, that are much below the maximum tolerable daily intake level
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48 established by the World Health Organization (1-4 pg TEQ kg⁻¹ day⁻¹) (van Leeuwen et al., 2000).
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54 The contribution of singles phases to TEQ depends on the gas-particle distribution in air samples. In
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56 2009 samples a high contribution to TEQ was given by the particulate phase (94%), while in 2012,
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58 when the G/P was very high, 98% of TEQ was represented by the gaseous phase. In 2009 air
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60 samples PCB-169 showed the greatest contribution to the total dioxin-like activity of the mixture,
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1 accounting for the 92% to TEQ; in gaseous phase PCN-73 gave a significant contribute (42%) to
2 TEQ, while toxicity of PM was due to the high concentration of PCB-169. In 2012, PCB-126 was
3 the most important contributor to TEQ (88%), giving toxicity to the mixture especially in gaseous
4 phase, while PCB-169 represent almost all TEQ (98%) of particulate matter; PCNs role was very
5 limited (<1% in gas, <2% in PM), because of their low concentration in air.
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11 **4. Conclusions**

12 Results showed a median concentration of 4.6 ng m⁻³ of PAHs, 0.99 ng m⁻³ of PCBs and 0.83 pg m⁻³
13 of PCNs in 2009 and 2.3 ng m⁻³ of PAHs, 0.35 ng m⁻³ of PCBs and 0.29 pg m⁻³ of PCNs in 2012.
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16 Generally, POPs analyzed were mostly in gas phase. G/P values were 3.2 and 7.6 for PAHs, 8.9 and
17 190 for PCBs and 0.91 and 22 for PCNs, in 2009 and 2012, respectively. We found PCB-11, a
18 marker of non-Aroclor contamination, for the first time in the Venetian Lagoon and in aerosol
19 samples from Europe. Gas-particle distribution of PAHs showed the typical pattern, with the
20 lightest congeners mainly concentrated in the gas phase and high molecular PAHs in particulate
21 phase. TeCBs and PeCBs dominated the PCBs. The evaluation of diagnostic ratios was useful to
22 estimate the sources of PAHs in Venice air: gasoline and diesel fuel combustion were likely the
23 most important sources of PAHs, while contributions from coal, wood or waste burning were less
24 probable. The presence of PCBs in Venice could be interpreted both from short- and long-range
25 atmospheric transport and PCBs composition was similar to the Aroclor 1248 and 1254 commercial
26 mixtures. In 2009 the high concentration of PCN-42 suggests a release of this congeners in the
27 Venice lagoon.
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51 The health effect of pollutants was evaluated using the Toxicological Equivalency method
52 developed by the World Health Organization. The assessment revealed that, although
53 benzo[a]pyrene was the main contributor to the total carcinogenic activity of PAHs, other congeners
54 can also significantly contribute to TCA. BaP concentration in particulate matter was under the
55 Italian limit value referred to PM₁₀. In this work we illustrated that also the total carcinogenic
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1 activity, calculated using all contributing congeners, summing those found in gas and particulate
2 phase, was below the Italian limit value. Due to the gas-particle distribution of PAHs, particulate
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4 matter gave a higher TCA than gas phase: high molecular weight congeners, that have higher
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6 carcinogenic activity than lower molecular weight PAH were distributed mainly in PM. The total
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8 dioxin-like activity of planar PCBs and PCNs was much below the daily intake level established by
9
10 the World Health Organization. PCB-126 and PCB-169 were the most important contributors to the
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12 TEQ value.
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17 **Acknowledgement**

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19 This work has been carried out with the financial support of the National Research Council (CNR).
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23
24 and Dr. Natalie Kehrwald of the University Ca' Foscari of Venice for their help.
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29 **Appendix**

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31 Table A.1 shows the sampling dates and the meteorological conditions during the sampling period.
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33 In Tables A.2 and A.3 the average field blanks (FB) and the limit of detection (LOD) for POPs are
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35 reported.
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26 27 28 29 Figure Captions

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31 Figure 1. Comparison of the total concentration (ng m^{-3}) of PAHs congeners (gaseous plus
32 particulate phases) during 2009 and 2012 campaign.
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36 Figure 2. Concentration (ng m^{-3}) of PAHs congeners, comparing gaseous and particulate phase
37 during: a) summer 2009; b) summer 2012.
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41 Figure 3. Comparison of the total concentration (ng m^{-3}) of PCBs categories (gaseous plus
42 particulate phases) during 2009 and 2012 campaign.
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46 Figure 4. Concentration (ng m^{-3}) of categories of PCBs based on chlorine number, comparing
47 gaseous and particulate phase, during a) summer 2009; b) summer 2012.
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51 Figure 5. PAHs plots of the diagnostic ratios: a) ANT/(ANT+PHE) versus FLA/(FLA+PYR); b)
52 CPAH/ \sum PAH versus BbF/BkF; c) BaA/(BaA+CHR) versus IcdP/(IcdP+BghiP) calculated using the
53 total concentration of PAHs congeners (gaseous plus particulate phases).
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Table 1. Atmospheric concentration (pg m^{-3}) of PAHs congeners in gaseous (G) and particulate (P) phases during the study and gas/particulate (G/P) ratio. Median (Range).

PAH	2009			2012		
	G	P	G/P	G	P	G/P
ACY	<LOD (<LOD-0.016)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0052)	3.1	0.0080 (0.0039-0.048)	0.0046 (<LOD-0.014)	1.7
ACE	0.020 (<LOD-0.064)	<LOD	n. d.	<LOD (<LOD-0.039)	<LOD (<LOD-0.020)	n. d.
FL	0.15 (0.043-0.34)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0094)	36	0.14 (0.054-0.29)	<LOD (<LOD-0.021)	20
PHE	1.6 (0.71-2.1)	0.034 (<LOD-0.14)	33	0.86 (0.38-1.4)	0.025 (0.014-0.056)	28
ANT	0.034 (<LOD-0.098)	0.0030 (<LOD-0.019)	14	0.023 (0.0066-0.059)	0.0025 (0.0015-0.0066)	11
FLA	0.97 (0.59-1.6)	0.056 (<LOD-0.24)	13	0.68 (0.29-1.1)	0.044 (0.022-0.10)	13
PYR	0.65 (0.38-0.98)	0.050 (<LOD-0.21)	9.4	0.46 (0.16-1.1)	0.051 (0.017-0.29)	9.5
B _a A	0.015 (0.0071-0.079)	0.024 (<LOD-0.10)	0.51	0.0057 (<LOD-0.027)	0.0085 (0.0047-0.034)	0.75
CHR	0.075 (0.048-0.27)	0.067 (<LOD-0.27)	1.1	0.043 (<LOD-0.10)	0.032 (0.020-0.082)	1.3
B _b F	0.0055 (0.0025-0.20)	0.091 (<LOD-0.37)	0.046	0.0019 (<LOD-0.010)	0.022 (0.014-0.065)	0.12
B _k F	<LOD	0.056	0.31	<LOD	0.0080	n. d.

	(<LOD-0.10)	(<LOD-0.18)		(<LOD-0.0010)	(<LOD-0.022)	
B_aP	<LOD (<LOD-0.18)	0.062 (<LOD-0.25)	n. d.	0.0028 (<LOD-0.0054)	0.016 (0.013-0.054)	0.16
B_{ghi}P	<LOD (<LOD-0.035)	0.16 (<LOD-0.61)	0.057	<LOD	0.025 (<LOD-0.092)	n. d.
I_{cd}P	<LOD	0.19 (<LOD-0.64)	n. d.	<LOD (<LOD-0.091)	<LOD (<LOD-0.17)	n. d.
D_{ah}A	<LOD (<LOD-0.052)	0.030 (<LOD-0.13)	0.41	<LOD (<LOD-0.00087)	0.0017 (<LOD-0.0081)	0.16
Σ₁₅PAH	3.9 (1.9-4.7)	0.82 (<LOD-3.2)	3.2	2.1 (0.94-4.2)	0.34 (0.12-1.0)	7.6

n. d.: not detectable

Table 2. Atmospheric concentration (pg m^{-3}) of some individual PCBs congeners (indicators and dioxin-like PCBs) and homologues of PCBs, in gaseous (G) and particulate (P) phases during the study and gas/particulate (G/P) ratio. Median (Range).

PCB	2009			2012		
	G	P	G/P	G	P	G/P
PCB-11	14 (<LOD-190)	1.1 (<LOD-5.9)	100	4.9 (2.7-6.5)	<LOD	n. d.
PCB-28	17 (9.4-42)	1.9 (<LOD-10)	11	5.6 (2.5-9.9)	0.028 (<LOD-0.088)	170
PCB-52	30 (25-39)	0.21 (<LOD-3.9)	91	9.0 (4.4-18)	<LOD (<LOD-0.078)	57
PCB-81	<LOD	<LOD	n. d.	0.16 (0.084-0.29)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0068)	59
PCB-77	1.7 (1.6-2.3)	<LOD (<LOD-0.082)	28	0.51 (0.26-0.97)	<LOD (<LOD-0.020)	37
PCB-84+101+90	44 (39-150)	<LOD (<LOD-98)	0.40	13 (5.8-24)	<LOD (<LOD-0.58)	34
PCB-123	0.64 (<LOD-1.5)	0.21 (<LOD-7.7)	1.8	0.21 (0.10-0.64)	0.0092 (<LOD-0.027)	18
PCB-118	11 (8.6-14)	0.21 (<LOD-4.5)	35	4.7 (2.4-9.8)	0.063 (<LOD-0.32)	39
PCB-114	<LOD (<LOD-0.30)	<LOD	n. d.	0.090 (0.051-0.17)	<LOD (<LOD-0.033)	6.2
PCB-105	9.1 (5.8-18)	2.1 (1.1-22)	3.8	1.4 (0.74-2.7)	0.028 (<LOD-0.12)	37

PCB-126	<LOD	<LOD (<LOD-0.23)	n. d.	0.051 (0.023-0.10)	<LOD (<LOD-0.013)	4.3
PCB-153	16 (12-20)	0.27 (<LOD-8.2)	38	5.5 (2.9-14)	<LOD (<LOD-0.21)	43
PCB-164+138	14 (11-17)	0.22 (<LOD-6.9)	40	5.3 (3.0-12)	<LOD (<LOD-0.20)	61
PCB-128+167	1.7 (1.5-2.2)	<LOD (<LOD-0.079)	19	0.62 (0.31-1.4)	0.00090 (<LOD-0.022)	44
PCB-156	0.50 (0.38-0.80)	0.041 (<LOD-0.30)	8.5	0.25 (0.10-0.57)	0.0091 (<LOD-0.012)	29
PCB-157	0.30 (0.13-0.59)	0.052 (<LOD-0.19)	3.1	0.059 (0.020-0.12)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0040)	7.6
PCB-169	<LOD (<LOD-0.21)	0.81 (0.33-14)	0.012	0.0056 (<LOD-0.016)	0.0028 (<LOD-0.0054)	1.6
PCB-180	3.6 (2.6-4.7)	0.22 (<LOD-4.0)	10	1.1 (0.65-3.9)	0.045 (<LOD-0.12)	19
PCB-189	<LOD	13 (<LOD-16)	n. d.	0.011 (<LOD-0.035)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0052)	2.0
MoCB	1.8 (0.090-6.0)	0.17 (<LOD-2.2)	2.7	0.093 (0.066-0.39)	0.014 (<LOD-0.066)	7.4
DiCB	58 (30-310)	2.2 (<LOD-8.0)	27	9.3 (4.3-14)	0.047 (<LOD-0.35)	170
TriCB	98 (61-240)	16 (4.5-110)	5.9	31 (15-51)	0.10 (<LOD-0.41)	180
TeCB	250	2.2	110	180	0.10	400

	(170-400)	(0.013-40)		(56-390)	(<LOD-0.69)	
PeCB	170 (130-260)	57 (2.1-100)	4.5	46 (23-90)	0.11 (0.0092-1.5)	110
HxCB	75 (59-97)	2.2 (0.33-46)	30	28 (15-70)	0.058 (0.016-0.77)	190
HpCB	19 (14-29)	26 (1.9-44)	1.2	5.7 (3.5-20)	0.095 (0.045-0.33)	57
OcCB	1.5 (1.2-2.2)	<LOD	n. d.	0.46 (0.24-1.5)	0.059 (<LOD-0.11)	10
NoCB	0.14 (<LOD-0.76)	0.38 (<LOD-4.5)	0.36	0.078 (<LOD-0.15)	<LOD	n. d.
DeCB	0.084 (<LOD-0.12)	<LOD	n. d.	0.050 (0.018-0.17)	0.0081 (<LOD-0.024)	5.7
Σ_{127} PCB	790 (470-1300)	120 (7.9-330)	8.9	350 (140-610)	0.95 (0.13-2.9)	190

n. d.: not detectable

Table 3. Atmospheric concentration (pg m^{-3}) of PCNs congeners in gaseous (G) and particulate (P) phase during the study and gas/particulate (G/P) ratio.

PCN	2009			2012		
	G	P	G/P	G	P	G/P
PCN-27	<LOD	<LOD (<LOD-0.071)	n. d.	0.062 (0.014-0.082)	<LOD (<LOD-0.037)	1.3
PCN-42	47 (<LOD-67)	40 (21-740)	1.0	0.049 (<LOD-0.43)	<LOD (<LOD-0.026)	2.2
PCN-52	<LOD	<LOD	n. d.	0.090 (0.013-0.27)	<LOD (<LOD-0.013)	26
PCN-67	<LOD (<LOD-0.38)	<LOD	n. d.	0.027 (<LOD-0.094)	<LOD (<LOD-0.0078)	8.0
PCN-73	0.62 (0.45-1.1)	<LOD (<LOD – 0.75)	1.6	0.0089 (<LOD-0.68)	<LOD (<LOD-0.024)	7.5
PCN-75	<LOD	<LOD	n. d.	0.0061 (<LOD-0.029)	<LOD (<LOD-0.045)	0.27
Σ_6 PCN	48 (0.92-67)	40 (21-740)	0.91	0.24 (0.027-1.0)	0.0085 (<LOD-0.14)	22

n. d.: not detectable

Table 4. Toxicological equivalent factors compared to BaP (TEF_{BaP}) and Benzo[a]pyrene equivalent (BaP_{eq}) concentration (pg m⁻³) for every PAH in gaseous (G), particulate (P) and total (gas plus particulate, G+P) phases.

PAH	TEF _{BaP} ^a	BaP _{eq} - 2009			BaP _{eq} - 2012		
		G	P	G+P	G	P	G+P
ACY	0.001	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.0080	0.0046	0.013
ACE	0.001	0.020	n. d.	0.020	n. d.	n. d.	0.020
FL	0.001	0.15	n. d.	0.15	0.14	n. d.	0.14
PHE	0.001	1.6	0.034	1.6	0.86	0.025	0.88
ANT	0.01	0.34	0.030	0.35	0.23	0.025	0.26
FLA	0.001	0.97	0.056	1.0	0.68	0.044	0.72
PYR	0.001	0.65	0.050	0.66	0.46	0.051	0.51
BaA	0.1	1.5	2.4	4.8	0.57	0.85	1.4
CHR	0.01	0.75	0.67	1.4	0.43	0.32	0.84
BbF	0.1	0.55	9.1	12	0.19	2.2	2.3
BkF	0.1	n. d.	5.6	10	n. d.	0.80	0.80
BaP	1	n. d.	62	93	2.8	16	22
BghiP	0.01	n. d.	1.6	1.6	n. d.	0.25	0.25
IcdP	0.1	n. d.	19	19	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.
DahA	1	n. d.	30	30	n. d.	1.7	1.7
TCA	-	6.6	130	180	6.4	23	31

^a Factors of Nisbet and Lagoy (1992).

n. d.: not detectable

Table 5. Toxicological equivalent factors compared to 2,3,7,8-TCDD (TEF_{TCDD}), 2,3,7,8-TCDD equivalent ($TCDD_{eq}$) concentration ($fg\ m^{-3}$) for dioxin-like PCBs and PCNs in gaseous (G), particulate (P) and total (gas plus particulate, G+P) phases.

PCB / PCN	TEF_{TCDD}^a	$TCDD_{eq}$ - 2009			$TCDD_{eq}$ - 2012		
		G	P	G+P	G	P	G+P
PCB-77	0.0001	0.17	n. d.	0.17	0.051	n. d.	0.053
PCB-81	0.0003	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.047	n. d.	0.047
PCB-126	0.1	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	5.1	n. d.	5.1
PCB-169	0.03	n. d.	24	24	0.17	0.084	0.32
PCB-105	0.00003	0.27	0.064	0.33	0.042	0.00084	0.043
PCB-114	0.00003	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.0027	n. d.	0.0030
PCB-118	0.00003	0.32	0.0064	0.39	0.14	0.0019	0.14
PCB-123	0.00003	0.019	0.0064	0.033	0.0064	0.00028	0.0071
PCB-156	0.00003	0.015	0.0012	0.020	0.0076	0.00027	0.0077
PCB-157	0.00003	0.0090	0.0016	0.0090	0.0018	n. d.	0.0018
PCB-128+167	0.00003	0.052	n. d.	0.052	0.019	0.00027	0.019
PCB-189	0.00003	n. d.	0.38	0.38	0.00032	n. d.	0.00036
PCN-67	0.001	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.027	n. d.	0.032
PCN-73	0.00101	0.63	n. d.	0.63	0.0090	n. d.	0.0090
TEQ (fg/m^3)	-	1.5	25	26	5.6	0.088	5.8

^a PCB: WHO-2005 TEF (Van den Berg et al., 2006); PCN: TEF from Luciferase assay (Jakobsson and Asplund, 2000).

Table A.1. Sampling dates, volumes and meteorological conditions (temperature, humidity and rain) during the sampling period.

Sample	Date	Volume (m³)	Temperature^a (°C)	Humidity^a (%)	Rainfall^b (mm)
1	3-5 August 2009	802.1	22.4	71	6.0
2	10-12 August 2009	851.2	22.9	79	9.6
3	17-19 August 2009	853.8	26.1	74	0.0
4	28-31 August 2009	1291.1	21.9	74	7.4
5	28-30 September 2009	783.3	20.7	83	0.0
6	2-4 July 2012	795.2	27.5	73	0.2
7	4-6 July 2012	867.6	26.6	71	0.0
8	16-18 July 2012	851.2	22.7	71	0.2
9	20-23 July 2012	1188.6	22.9	68	0.0
10	24-26 July 2012	862.0	24.4	77	0.0
11	27-30 July 2012	1290.1	26.5	78	0.0
12	01-03 August 2012	834.0	27.1	66	0.0
13	03-06 August 2012	1070.5	26.5	79	0.0
14	10-12 September 2012	827.3	23.9	79	26.2
15	19-21 September 2012	937.0	17.0	69	27.8
16	01-03 October 2012	830.3	19.3	84	17.8

^a Median of the daily parameters associated to the sampling dates.

^b Total rainfall during the sampling days.

Datas are given by the Porto Marghera Industrial Zone Institution (Ente Zona Industriale Porto Marghera).

Table A.2. Average field blanks (FB) for PAHs (ng), PCBs (pg) and PCNs (pg). G: gaseous phase; P: particulate phase.

	FB 2009 (ng)		FB 2012 (ng)	
PAHs	G	P	G	P
ACY	12	1.4	0.73	0.81
ACE	7.7	7.0	8.6	7.4
FL	3.9	6.1	8.0	6.0
PHE	6.8	6.3	12	8.2
ANT	1.1	1.5	0.41	0.28
FLA	1.2	0.71	4.8	4.3
PYR	1.3	0.65	6.6	7.1
BaA	0.21	0.98	0.21	0.42
CHR	0.37	n. d.	0.83	0.96
BbF	0.26	0.10	0.80	0.86
BkF	0.14	0.10	0.21	0.57
BaP	0.86	0.080	3.4	3.4
BghiP	n. d.	n. d.	4.3	3.9
IcdP	2.7	0.10	25	23
DahA	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.51
	FB 2009 (pg)		FB 2012 (pg)	
PCBs	G	P	G	P
PCB-11	230	470	380	220
PCB-28	1800	290	77	52
PCB-52	190	95	83	55
PCB-81	n. d.	n. d.	3.4	1.6
PCB-77	n. d.	n. d.	4.8	2.5

PCB-84+101+90	120	80	290	150
PCB-123	n. d.	33	6.3	1.3
PCB-118	n. d.	14	96	41
PCB-114	n. d.	n. d.	2.8	2.0
PCB-105	n. d.	13	24	8.9
PCB-126	1200	520	n. d.	0.27
PCB-153	62	33	110	63
PCB-164+138	11	18	100	57
PCB-128+167	n. d.	n. d.	8.7	5.0
PCB-156	n. d.	n. d.	4.0	3.2
PCB-157	31	64	0.90	0.26
PCB-169	n. d.	10	0.48	0.29
PCB-180	n. d.	n. d.	30	26
PCB-189	6300	13000	0.63	0.21
	FB 2009 (pg)		FB 2012 (pg)	
PCNs	G	P	G	P
PCN-27	n. d.	n. d.	5.6	n. d.
PCN-42	120	n. d.	7.7	n. d.
PCN-52	n. d.	n. d.	3.1	0.57
PCN-67	n. d.	n. d.	0.38	0.76
PCN-73	n. d.	n. d.	0.58	0.15
PCN-75	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.

n. d. : not detectable

Table A.3. Limit of detection (LOD) for PAHs (ng), PCBs (pg) and PCNs (pg). G: gaseous phase; P: particulate phase.

	LOD 2009 (ng)		LOD 2012 (ng)	
	G	P	G	P
PAHs				
ACY	12	3.3	1.8	1.4
ACE	23	16	24	11
FL	17	12	21	8
PHE	24	14	29	11
ANT	1.8	1.8	1.1	0.37
FLA	11	8.7	15	7.0
PYR	16	16	21	12
BaA	0.67	2.0	0.68	0.77
CHR	1.4	1.3	1.9	1.4
BbF	1.8	1.7	2.3	1.4
BkF	0.62	2.3	0.69	1.3
BaP	3.1	2.9	5.7	4.3
BghiP	13	17	18	9.7
IcdP	74	88	96	53
DahA	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	0.51
	LOD 2009 (pg)		LOD 2012 (pg)	
PCBs	G	P	G	P
PCB-11	1200	670	807	290
PCB-28	6900	330	170	63
PCB-52	430	160	169	78
PCB-81	n. d.	n. d.	8.9	3.2
PCB-77	n. d.	n. d.	12	5.8

PCB-84+101+90	250	370	968	242
PCB-123	n. d.	38	25	3.1
PCB-118	n. d.	82	343	64
PCB-114	n. d.	n. d.	14	5.2
PCB-105	n. d.	40	96	18
PCB-126	3600	520	n. d.	0.92
PCB-153	320	120	334	92
PCB-164+138	58	130	275	93
PCB-128+167	n. d.	n. d.	25	8.5
PCB-156	n. d.	n. d.	11	4.4
PCB-157	160	65	5.6	0.7
PCB-169	n. d.	10	2.2	0.54
PCB-180	n. d.	n. d.	88	39
PCB-189	33000	13000	2.9	0.72
	LOD 2009 (pg)		LOD 2012 (pg)	
PCNs	G	P	G	P
PCN-27	n. d.	n. d.	5.6	n. d.
PCN-42	640	n. d.	19	n. d.
PCN-52	n. d.	n. d.	8.5	1.2
PCN-67	n. d.	n. d.	2.0	1.4
PCN-73	n. d.	n. d.	3.0	0.41
PCN-75	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.	n. d.

n. d. : not detectable

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Figure 2

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST – DECLARATION

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